

Nanomaterial grouping: Unraveling the relationship of induced mechanisms and potency at a temporal scale

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ABSTRACT

Grouping is a fundamental step to generalize engineered nanomaterials (ENM) hazard. However, most strategies lack comprehensiveness in ENM and experimental settings. Toxicogenomics allows the characterization of the direct molecular mechanisms of action (MOA) associated to ENM hazard. In this study, we implemented an adverse outcome pathway (AOP)-based framework for ENM grouping. We hypothesized that AOP-direct MOA along with ENM potency, i.e., the dose required to activate a molecular response, could be used to robustly group distinct ENM exposures by considering a mechanistic and multiscale level of response. Our results highlighted a critical role of the exposure duration and ENM potency respectively on the specificity and progression of the response. Moreover, we investigated the complexity and time scale of the biological events triggered by ENM. In particular, genotoxicity-related AOPs were found triggered at longer exposures. Higher ENM potency was linked to shorter exposure and basic and starting events. While lower potency was linked to prolonged exposures and advanced stages of biological processes. Our results also highlighted shared molecular responses in groups of ENM both at shorter (5 clusters) and longer (3 clusters) exposure periods. Based on computed features for cluster predictions, grouping could have likely resulted from the influence of chemical composition, size-dependent properties of ENM, and biological descriptors. Finally, features were interdependent and differed in quantity and connectivity, indicating differences in the response dynamics. Notably, our study does not include every ENM currently available. Hereby, our findings pave the way for the construction of quantitative AOPs and hold significant implications for ENM hazard assessment and regulatory decision-making.

Introduction

The growing production and variety of ENM demands the development of New Approach Methodologies (NAM) to assess ENM hazard in a prompt and accurate manner and support Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) approaches [1,2]. Transcriptomics offers a convenient way to identify early indications of biological responses (including toxicity) and to prevent potential adverse health effects [3,4]. Toxicogenomics has proven useful for determining the MOA induced by ENM [5].

ENM grouping and read-across are key strategies that allow the prediction of potential hazards for ENM within the same group, avoiding a substantial quantity of testing while accounting for ENM complexity

[6–8]. Current grouping strategies for ENM often consider similarity of their physicochemical properties [9] and biological activities (toxicity assays [10] and multi-omics data [11]). ENM grouping has often been performed considering equivalent experimental settings of exposure or targeted approaches (toxicity endpoints) [12]. However, ENM grouping should be comprehensive enough to account for the variability of responses and provide mechanistic insights into hazards commonly shared between ENM [13]. In this light, we used a heterogeneous collection of transcriptomic ENM exposure studies (e.g., ENM chemistry, biological system, dose ranges, and exposure time) and assessed the influence of exposure duration and ENM potency in the triggered molecular responses [14].

Traditionally, toxic effects have been associated with the dose of

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exposure to determine doses needed to trigger a response [15], such as benchmark dose (BMD) [16]. Previous studies have shown associations between BMD and gene expression alterations, suggesting that this concept can be translated to the molecular level and hence reflect direct MOA induced by exposure to the material [17,18]. In a recent study, distinct ENM have been ranked based on their potency to activate a molecular response, represented by transcriptional BMDs (tBMDs) [19].

In toxicogenomics, pathway enrichment analysis has often been used to anchor gene expression alterations to a phenotype [20,21]. Yet, these approaches may be less effective in providing mechanistic insights at multiscale/hierarchical level, which could be linked to apical endpoints. The AOP framework describes a sequence of causally linked key events (KEs) [22]. An AOP starts with a molecular initiating event (MIE) and progresses to an adverse outcome (AO) through different levels of biological organization [23]. Current undertakings have shown the potential of integrating tBMD with MWCNT-lung fibrosis AOP. Another study has correlated tBMDs with ENM properties but limited to part of the same AOP to group distinct MWCNT [24,25]. The recent molecular annotation of human health-related AOPs has bridged the gap in deriving mechanistic knowledge from toxicogenomics data [26].

Here, we present a novel strategy to guide the assessment of ENM. We modeled system sensitivity using dose-dependent analysis to link activating doses to enriched events in the AOP framework. Considering multiple toxicogenomic studies, we observed that our approach provides a holistic view of ENM induced response. It effectively accounted for the complexity of the biological response in the grouping by supporting factors already highlighted in existing literature. Unlike previous studies, this integrative approach allowed us to assess nanomaterial hazard in a mechanistic and multiscale manner, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the biological response. In addition, it synthesized data from multiple studies to find meaningful patterns. Therefore, we categorize ENM based on their MOA by combining grouping, AOP concepts, and dose-dependent transitions.

We analyzed genome-wide expression data previously curated by Saarimäki et al. (2021) focusing on exposure studies centered on a multi-dose design [27]. This collection included ENM with heterogeneous physicochemical characteristics tested in multiple experimental settings. First, we investigated the integrated influence of potency and induced MOA at a temporal scale in the context of the AOP framework. Then, we identified groups of ENM with common patterns of molecular responses based on a consensus hierarchical clustering. Finally, we determined factors that drive the ENM grouping. This holistic approach not only addresses the complexities of ENM hazard assessment but also aligns with the adoption of NAM, thereby contributing to a SSbD of ENM.

Methods

Dataset selection and analysis

Here, an exposure study is considered as the combination of gene expression data series identifier (i.e., a unique GEO accession number of a series of related samples obtained from GEO database represented by GSEXXX) and material exposed. On the other hand, an experiment is the combination of exposure study and time point tested. In this study, we utilized gene expression data previously curated by Saarimäki et al. (2021) [27]. The original collection of curated transcriptomic dataset (10.5281/zenodo.7980953) comprised a total of 101 ENM exposure studies, including the GEO accession numbers for each corresponding study [27]. For each experiment, the collection offers the pre-processed gene expression values, the result of differential gene expression analysis, and ENM descriptors. For each experiment, the collection offers the pre-processed gene expression values, the result of differential gene expression analysis, and ENM descriptors. Subsequently, we selected studies that assessed multiple dose levels of exposures. Eventually, 64 exposure studies (corresponding to 114 experimental settings) matched

our selection criteria (Table S1) [27]. Then, these studies were considered for the dose-dependency modeling and transcriptional BMDs determination [27].

The datasets were highly diverse in terms of experimental settings, such as exposure type (*ex vivo*, *in vitro* and *in vivo*), biological system, tissue (lung, gastrointestinal, and liver), material tested, exposure time (from 1 hour up to 1 year). Selected datasets included metal oxides, such as copper and titanium in varied forms and surface functionalization; noble metals, such as gold and silver-based ENM; tube and sphere-shaped carbon-based; silica-based with various surface chemistries; and polymeric-based ENM. In addition to the experimental ENM descriptors of the respective exposures, a list of 159 predicted intrinsic and extrinsic nanodescriptors including molecular, electronic, and atomistic descriptors were extracted from a recent analysis (10.5281/zenodo.7674574) [28]. Such descriptors consider ENM colloidal stability (n - number of ENM in the analyzed agglomerate and S - the number of surface elements) and nano bio interface interactions (A.GLY...kB.300 K, A.ETA...kB.300k, A.DGL...kB.300 K).

Differentially expressed genes (DEGs) identified by Saarimäki et al. (2021) served as the initial dataset for this study [29]. These DEGs were subsequently filtered considering an absolute \log_2 fold change higher than 0.58 and False Discovery Rate (FDR)-adjusted p-value lower than 0.05. This filtering process ensured that only the most significant DEGs were included in our further analyses. There were 16,168 unique significantly DEGs. Given that each ENM is exposed to biological systems with multiple doses, this criterion should be met at least once per exposure time. Furthermore, for the same studies, we performed a dose-dependent analysis to identify DEGs whose expression values also show an increasing or decreasing trend across the different exposure doses. The dose-dependent analysis was conducted using the BMDx tool [30]. For every gene, various models were fitted. The optimal model was chosen based by means of the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). For the same gene, the model with lowest AIC value was selected to estimate effective doses such as the BMD, its lower (BMDL) and upper (BMDU) bound values. Genes with BMD, BMDL, BMDU values that were beyond the tested dose range were filtered. Moreover, genes whose ratio between the predicted dose were higher than the estimated values were also filtered out ($BMD/BMDL > 20$, $BMDU/BMD > 20$, and $BMDU/BMDL > 40$). Finally, for each experiment, the set of DEGs that were also dose-dependent (DD-DEG) were identified. We have identified a total of 10,842 unique DD-DEG in our data. Eventually, only 55 exposure studies encompassing 87 experimental conditions had at least one DEG with a significant dose-response relationship (see **Supplementary file 1.csv**).

To make ENM exposures more comparable and reduce bias from different exposure dose ranges chosen by each exposure study, transcriptional BMDL were normalized by exposure study considering minimum and maximum doses utilized. Because genes could originate from mouse, mouse ensembl gene id were mapped to human ensembl id by using biomaRt package (v2.40.1). Genes that were not mapped to any human genes or that mapped to multiple human genes were discarded and only those that mapped one-to-one were considered.

Data harmonization

For the analysis, BMDL was chosen as the parameter of interest because it is considered a more conservative estimate of the effective dose and preventive of any health effect. Since the doses tested for the different ENM were not comparable between each other, the BMDL values of DD-DEG were normalized in the range 0–1 based on their respective experimental settings (minimum and maximum doses used by each exposure study). Numeric experimental and predicted nanodescriptors were obtained from a previous study (10.5281/zenodo.7674574) and harmonized by removing non-numeric characters and computing the mean whenever there were a minimum and a maximum value associated to the ENM feature [28].

AOP and KE enrichment

Enrichment analysis was carried out using Fisher's exact test, as implemented in the `enrich` function from R package `bc3net` [31] (v1.0.4) for DD-DEG of each experiment against the gene annotations to of AOP and KE (10.5281/zenodo.7980953)[26]. AOP and KE was considered significantly enriched if FDR-adjusted p-value was lower than 0.05. Background genes consisted of all genes measured in that experiment. BMDL values were aggregated and linked to the enriched KE by computing their average value based on the corresponding BMDL values of each gene annotated to the KE. An AOP was deemed significantly enriched if both the AOP itself and at least 50 % of the enriched KEs were significantly enriched. A directed KE-KE relationship network was built using the edge list from AOP-Wiki (August 2022). `igraph` (v1.3.1) package was used for visualization.

Functional categorization of KE from AOP-Wiki

KE have been downloaded from AOP-Wiki (August 2022, <http://aopwiki.org/>). Human relevant KE from AOP-Wiki were manually categorized into functional effects across different levels of the biological hierarchy to avoid misattribution at the AOP level and account for KE repetitions and conduct informed interpretations about ENM-induced MOA. This manual customized functional annotation of each KE was performed by grouping KEs with similar biological effects, including but were not limited to genotoxicity, xenobiotic response, and dysregulated lipid metabolism (see **Supplementary file 2.csv**). Assignment of a functional category to a KE were based on the connection of each KE to the corresponding AOPs to which they belong and their specific characteristics and implication within the biological context. One KE could be assigned to more than one functional category.

Feature enrichment

Features that describe annotated KE in the AOP-Wiki (<https://aopwiki.org/>) concerning KE stage and scale were utilized to determine the specific moment and the level of biological complexity where certain events are more prominently overrepresented over the course of the biological response. Within the AOP framework, KE stage consists of a specific step or event in a sequence of linked KE that occurs from exposure to an insult to an adverse effect, and KE scale describes the level of biological organization in which a specific event occurs. To obtain the KE stage and scale, we extracted KE type and level of biological organization associated to each KE from AOP-Wiki (August 2022, <https://aopwiki.org/>). Next, we computed the KE stage at which a KE happens for those KE categorized as KE and those assigned more than one category. This was performed by computing the relative position of KE between the shortest path connecting the enriched MIE and AO nodes within a specific enriched AOP. To identify overrepresented features, such as KE stage and scale in the context of AOP framework, we conducted a one-sided Fisher's exact test per feature. We associated a feature with a KE if the AOP which this KE is part of was considered significantly enriched for the specific experiment.

For each exposure period, we labeled KE as 'low' if their average values of BMDL were below (or equal) to the median value of all BMDL linked to enriched KE of the ENM exposure study. Otherwise, if the average value of BMDL was above the median, we labeled the KE as 'high'. Then, features, such as low and high dose were enriched in each KE stage and scale separately per exposure period and combined exposure period (short-term and intermediate-term).

Consensus similarity score and clustering

We computed a consensus similarity matrix for short-term and intermediate-term exposure periods to robustly identify common patterns of response between distinct ENM exposures. To achieve this, we

combined distinct similarity metrics into one. We considered five metrics according to the data type, i.e. if it was binary or continuous data. Binary data consisted of presence and absence of KE (enriched or not in the exposure study), while continuous data included ENM potency values linked to the enriched KE. Jaccard Index, overlap coefficient, and cosine distance were used as binary similarities measures; weighted Jaccard Index, weighted overlap coefficient, and cosine distance were used as continuous similarity measures [32]. Therefore, pairwise similarity was computed between exposure studies for each exposure period producing three similarity matrices. We utilized the `netdist` function from the R `nettools` package (v1.1.0) to calculate the Ipsen-Mikhailov distance among the three similarity matrices [33]. Then, we combined them by averaging according to their distances in a hierarchical manner. These steps were performed to each data type. The consensus similarity matrix score of exposure-to-exposure study was then computed by averaging the binary and continuous matrices (i.e., presence and absence of enriched KE and ENM potency associated to the KE). Finally, based on the exposure-to-exposure consensus similarity score, agglomerative hierarchical clustering was performed using the ward. D2 linkage criteria for each exposure period determining clusters of ENM exposure studies with similar biological response [34].

XGboost framework for cluster prediction, feature contribution, and interaction

We established classification tasks wherein we utilized exposure characteristics as features to predict corresponding groupings. Our aim was to discern the key parameters driving the biological response contributing to SSBD by employing a well-performing predictor of the grouping variable based on these characteristics. To achieve this, we trained a gradient boosting classifier for each exposure period, consisting of 5000 trees with a maximum depth of 50 levels [35,36]. This setup enabled the classifiers to effectively capture interactions among the features. Each classification task underwent evaluation through 5-fold cross-validation, repeated 10 times. We excluded features with different increasing percentages of missing data from the training since features with no value could introduce bias and affect performance of the models (see **Table S1** for more details).

In addition to traditional model evaluation techniques (e.g., train and test accuracy), we employed SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) values to gain insights into the importance of each feature in the classification process [37]. SHAP values quantifies the contribution of each feature to the model's predictions. It evaluates every possible combination of feature values. Measuring SHAP values allowed us to determine the relevance of each exposure characteristic in driving the classification outcomes, thereby providing valuable insights into the underlying mechanisms.

Furthermore, we utilized SHAP values to analyze feature interactions, exploring how the effects of different exposure characteristics combine to influence the classification decisions. By examining the SHAP interaction values, we gained a nuanced understanding of how pairs or groups of features interacted to affect the biological response. This comprehensive analysis not only enhanced our understanding of the individual contributions of each feature but also provide crucial insights into the complex interplay between features, ultimately enriching the interpretability of our classification models.

Features used to build this model were ranked in decreasing order of values of data completeness and average feature contribution. To achieve a consensus rank, each variable was assigned equal weight and the Borda method from the R package `TopKLists`, was applied. Finally, the median was then used to obtain the ranking.

Results and discussion

Identification of relevant experimental studies for ENM grouping

The transcriptional MOA of a substance refers to the molecular changes induced upon its exposure compared to the control condition. In

toxicogenomics, classical differential expression analysis has often been used to determine changes in transcription comparing exposed and unexposed conditions [3,38]. Recently, BMD modeling has also gained ground in this field to determine direct changes caused by ENM exposure [24,39]. We hypothesized that expression levels of genes are influenced by the dose and therefore dose-dependent alterations can be interpreted

Fig. 1. Description of data collection used in this study. a) number of ENM exposure studies based on exposure period, b) number of ENM exposure studies based on exposure period separated by exposure type and tissue, c) number of ENM exposure studies based on exposure period separated by exposure type and chemistry.

as the direct MOA of the ENM. Therefore, dose-dependent genes are genes whose expression values show an increasing or decreasing trend across the different exposure doses.

Fig. 1 summarizes the number of ENM exposure studies that have a multiple-dose centered design separated by tissue, exposure type and chemistry. ENM under consideration are characterized by different physicochemical characteristics (e.g., core composition, surface chemistry, size) and experimental conditions including different settings in terms of exposure time, type, tissue, cell line, and exposed material. Indeed, this diversity in the experimental conditions and ENM is relevant because it offers a more comprehensive view on ENM hazard potential. Although the data is extensive, it does not cover all existing ENM, and there might be imbalances in the data. In addition, spatio-temporal variation is important to comprehend how the dynamic of nano bio interface interactions impact the mechanisms elicited by ENM exposure [40].

Direct effects induced by exposure to ENM have been obtained considering genes that are DD-DEG [17]. We hypothesized that linking DD-DEG to KEs of the AOP framework provides mechanistic and multiscale interpretation of the direct ENM induced MOA. To characterize the direct MOA for each ENM, we conducted enrichment analysis of KEs for the DD-DEG identified in each experiment, independently. 40 out of 55 exposures had at least one statistically significant KE enrichment totaling 54 experimental conditions. For instance, 5 out 8 KEs related to AOP:173 were overrepresented among the genes responding to exposure to MWCNT. Of these, KEs, such as “Increased, fibroblast proliferation and myofibroblast differentiation” and “Accumulation, collagen” were overrepresented which are consistent with fibrosis involved processes [41]. Another example, half of KEs associated to AOP:282 were overrepresented in silver-based ENM. “Oxidation of membrane lipids” and “ROS generation from photoactivated chemicals” were evident, which is also characteristic of photocatalytic activity of noble metals [42,43]. Therefore, the obtained results align with findings previously reported in the literature, thereby supporting their plausibility and validity.

Mechanisms induced by ENM are time-dependent

ENM hazard is dependent on the duration of the exposure [44–46]. However, information on whether specific responses occur at a particular time interval has been fragmented. In this study, we aimed at understanding the impact of the exposure duration on the response of biological systems. We hypothesized that specific mechanistic responses can be found at shorter and longer time points. To test this hypothesis, we compared the results of the KE enrichment analysis from ENM exposure with various durations. Different exposure time ranges were defined based on the type of exposure (*in vitro*, *in vivo*, and *ex vivo*) due to the distinct sensitivity of different biological systems, in line with [23], Figure S1 [28].

We obtained 29, 18 and 3 exposure studies at short-, intermediate-, and long-term, respectively (Figure S2). The majority of significant KE enrichment was found in short-term and intermediate-term exposure. Only three studies were categorized as long-term exposure and there was a lack of significantly enriched KEs, which resulted in their exclusion from further analysis. Our analysis shows that there is a limited amount of available data for long-term exposures. Thus, more data are needed to extend our study to long-term effects. This may be due to the experimental setup which does not include repeated exposures strengthening the hypothesis that the system may be recovering or has recovered. Hence, performing repeated exposures, measuring pathology-related endpoints (e.g., histological changes), or analyzing epigenetic modifications could be more appropriate, all of which are not part of the scope of this study.

Based on these results, we selected ENM exposure datasets encompassing short-term and intermediate-term exposures totaling 51 experimental conditions. Significantly enriched KEs per experiment were merged per exposure period (e.g., short-term and intermediate-term). To

assess whether the MOA induced by ENM is time dependent we considered two aspects of the biological response: (i) the specificity, i.e. a biological response that occurs exclusively within an exposure period and (ii) responsiveness/sensitivity, i.e. the effective dose of ENM needed to the exposed system to react to the stimulus.

We aimed at identifying KEs covering similar biological effects specifically altered at short- and intermediate-term exposures. Thus, we categorized the KEs in 51 groups (Supplementary file_2.csv) and then investigated how these groups are presented across the short-term and intermediate-term studies (Fig. 2). Our results show that genotoxicity-related KEs are found only altered at intermediate-term exposure (Fig. 2). Since this is the only category that showed time-dependent specificity in its response (KE ratio at short-term = 0, KE ratio at intermediate-term = 0.68), we focused on this in the subsequent discussion. Genotoxicity KEs refer to specific events that occur from a substance causing direct damage by binding to DNA or by indirect interaction with byproducts from metabolism. This functional category also encompasses subsequent effects of DNA damage, such as heritable alterations, DNA adducts and strand breaks. In line with this, genetic effects have been reported in previous studies for TiO₂ [47], SiO₂ [48], CuO [49], and MWCNT-based ENM [50] in similar exposure range time as depicted here. These effects have been attributed mainly to the persistence of ENM in the biological system and induced oxidative stress. It is possible that the variability in the persistence and hence effects in the organism after exposure to ENM, could depend on whether the ENM is based on essential (e.g. copper) or non-essential (e.g., carbon, titanium, and silica) nutrient. Organisms might have natural mechanisms to metabolize copper from copper-based ENM, allowing for more efficient clearance. In contrast, titanium or carbon-based ones could not be as readily processed, possibly leading to longer persistence and greater effects. A recent study demonstrated that responses to various metal-based ENM are similar to those of their corresponding metal ions [51]. This similarity in response applied to both essential and non-essential metal-based ENM. Furthermore, this held true regardless of their known physiological function, whether essential or not.

Representing AOPs as KE-KE network can offer mechanistic insights at multiscale level, highlighting the cascade and interconnectivity of KE spanning various levels of organization in the biological system. AOP networks have been obtained by joining individual AOPs from AOP-Wiki (see Methods), which share events, and therefore this representation enables to capture multiple degrees of the biological complexity [52]. In order to explore the connectivity of genotoxicity-related KEs, we mapped them onto the KE-KE network and highlighted the AOPs in which they are included (Fig. 3). Only AOPs of minimum four KEs with at least 50 % enriched were considered. We obtained 323 KEs and 341 key event relationships (KER). As many as 58 KEs and 51 KERs were found specifically at short-term, while 123 KEs and 107 KERs were obtained at intermediate-term. AOPs usually include a range of biological events. Given the multiscale and diversity of the biological response represented by AOPs, no limitations were imposed in the number of genotoxicity-related KE within the enriched AOP.

Next, we hypothesized that enriched genotoxicity-related AOPs have genotoxic related KEs as central components directly causing genetic damage or genotoxic related KEs as secondary components indirectly influencing genotoxic outcomes. Indeed, in some cases they were the main component of the AOP such as in AOP:46 (*Mutagenic Mode-of-Action leading to Hepatocellular Carcinoma*), AOP:139 (*Alkylation of DNA leading to cancer*), AOP:397 (*Bulky DNA adducts leading to mutations*), AOP:296 (*Oxidative DNA damage leading to chromosomal aberrations and mutations*), and AOP:322 (*Alkylation of DNA leading to reduced sperm count*). In other cases, they only contributed to the AO, in which primary KEs set off a cascade that eventually led to DNA damage. This was mainly evident in AOP:409 (*Frustrated phagocytosis leads to malignant mesothelioma*) and AOP:272 (*Deposition of energy leading to lung cancer*), see Fig. 3.

We observed that KEs enriched in the same exposure duration are

Fig. 2. Ratio of association of the functional categories to short- and intermediate-term exposures. Functional categories are clustered based on the ratio of uniquely enriched KEs with respect to the total (enriched and non-enriched) of KEs in each functional category. A functional category represents functionally similar KEs. A gradient color ranges from dark blue to white is used to represent the highest to the lowest ratio, where dark blue means that all the KEs belonging to the same functional category are found in the same time range. Boxes are used to highlight functional categories that are specific of an exposure duration.

often found connected in the network (Fig. 3), indicating that consecutive KEs often occur at the same time scale. To quantify this, we tested the hypothesis that an association may exist between the duration of the exposure and the biological scale of the altered KE. The biological scale (molecular, cellular, tissue, individual, and population) has been described in the AOP-Wiki for each KE. No significant enrichment of KE stage or biological scale was identified in a specific time-point (Fig. 4A and B). That is, there was not a trend of starting and basic events (represented by KE of type MIE and at molecular/cellular level) over-represented at shorter time points or later and advanced events (represented by KE of type AO and at tissue/organ/individual level) at longer time points. In contrast to what has been typically observed in the AOP framework, our result suggests that the experiments do not capture the time scale of response, in which events induced by the ENM exposures do not unfold or propagate over time.

Next, we addressed the sensitivity of the biological system based on ENM potency as represented by the BMDL values. For each KE, we defined the ENM potency as the average BMDL value of the dose-dependent genes associated with it. The ENM potency is a function of the response sensitivity of a biological system to its exposure. To determine if there were significant differences in sensitivity between short-term and intermediate-term exposures, we investigated the

distribution of BMDL values associated with enriched KE of each ENM exposure per exposure duration. Our analysis shows that higher ENM potency is associated with shorter exposure duration, whereas lower potency to prolonged exposure (Fig. 4C and D), which agrees with Labib et al. [24]. In that study, the authors pointed out that lower potency values could indicate a proximity to an advanced stage of an AOP, meaning that would be close to the AO manifestation. In addition, another study identified pronounced cell-cell communication after acute exposure to ENM and at a lesser extent as the time progressed in a few cases, indicating the influence of biological layers on the attenuation of the response [53]. Of note, all intermediate-term exposures considered here result from one insult exposure instead of repeated exposures, therefore it is important to acknowledge the influence of the experimental setup. In this light, low potency could also be a consequence of the recovery of the system to the insult, weakening its response. It is worth noting that our finding does not imply that shorter exposure studies commonly use lower doses and longer exposure studies use higher ENM doses. In acute toxicity assays, higher doses are typically used, whereas in chronic studies, lower doses are employed to ensure survival over the study period. To avoid bias from experimental setups we normalized potency values considering the dose interval used in the corresponding exposure study.

Fig. 3. Temporal AOP network representation. Subgraph of the AOP network including specifically enriched KEs of ENM exposure studies at different exposure duration: short-term (yellow) and intermediate-term (purple) and commonly (grey). Genotoxicity-related KEs are highlighted in green and corresponding regions associated to certain AOPs are enclosed with dashed lines. KEs are represented by nodes and KE relationships (KER) are represented by directed edges, and average BMDL linked to the KEs are represented by node size.

Time does not affect the progression of events in the AOP framework, but potency does

Since we identified time-dependent response of the biological system to the ENM potency, we sought to test whether there is an association between ENM potency and stage of response (e.g. MIE, KE or AO), as well as between ENM potency and biological scale of response (e.g., molecular, cellular). To this end, KE were labeled in “low” and “high” based on the dose needed to trigger a response. Under these conditions, potent ENM would require lower doses to trigger a molecular response and less potent ones, higher doses.

For both short- and intermediate-term, we observed that KEs with lower triggering doses (BMDL) were associated with basic (molecular, cellular) and initiating events (MIE), while KEs with higher BMDL were

associated with advanced stages (tissue, organ, individual) and AO (Fig. 5A and B). Given these findings, we next hypothesized that at an advanced stage of response (i.e., AO and high biological scale KE), lower potency could be associated to the tolerance/adaptation and resilience of the biological system due to the interaction of biological layers and biomolecules with ENM surface that add complexity to the biological interactions ultimately resulting in a diluted response [54]. Bio-corona has been known to be formed around ENM upon encounter with biological system and it may offer a protective effect [54]. In addition, the complexity of the bio-corona can be greater when different levels of biological organization and exposure system are contemplated in ENM exposures [14]. An investigation into the difference of susceptibility from different subpopulations has concluded that genetic diversity could also affect the obtained effective doses [55].

Fig. 4. Exposure duration does not affect the progression of events in the AOP framework, but it influences ENM potency. A) Enrichment score ($-\log_{10}(\text{p-value})$) of p-values were computed across experiments using one-sided Fisher's test for statistical significance to identify timewise enriched stages of the response. B) Enrichment score ($-\log_{10}(\text{p-value})$) of p-values were computed across experiments using one-sided Fisher's test for statistical significance to identify timewise enriched biological scale of the response. C) Distribution of average BMDL values of KEs enriched across experiments at short- and intermediate-term used to perform the further statistical analysis. D) Student's *t*-test between average BMDL values from KEs enriched across experiments at short and intermediate-term highlights a statistically significant difference. KEs were considered collectively across all exposure at each exposure duration. Values above red dashed line mark features that have a p-value lower than 0.05, indicating significant enrichment. The symbol "*" indicates a significant difference between short-term and intermediate-term exposure.

Different ENM exposures elicit common patterns of molecular response

ENM grouping is not always straightforward since ENM-induced biological effects usually change depending on ENM characteristics, such as size, surface chemistry, or shape. Upon contact with the biological environment, ENM acquires a new biological identity that is context-dependent and hence differs from its synthetic identity. This interaction with the environment could also mask the original features of the ENM, posing an additional challenge [56]. This acquired identity could result in ENM sharing similar biological responses despite not exhibiting analogous physicochemical characteristics. Yet studies have shown that pristine ENM properties influence biological effects [40]. As ENM bio-corona evolves over time in the surrounding environment, it may also influence its potency to cause an adverse effect [54]. Building upon this concept and the fact that ENM response has shown to be time-dependent, we kept the analysis of short-term and intermediate-term effects separated and hypothesized that ENM grouping is dependent on the direct MOA induced by the exposure and the potency of its response.

To assess if there are ENM exposure studies with similar potential hazards, we conducted a hierarchical clustering of ENM exposures studies at short-term and intermediate-term. ENM exposure studies from short-term and intermediate-term comprised 29 and 18 exposure studies, respectively (Figure S2). We employed a consensus approach in the hierarchical clustering to capture a more robust relationship between ENM exposures and incorporate various facets of the ENM-induced response. For each exposure duration, multiple similarity measures between exposures studies considering (i) presence and

absence of enrichment, represented by binary data and (ii) average BMDL linked to enriched KE, represented by continuous data, were used to build similarity matrices. The distance between each similarity matrix for each data type and exposure duration were computed separately using the Ipsen-Mikhailov method (Figure S3 includes Ipsen-Mikhailov comparison of similarity matrices obtained by varied metrics, for more details see Methods). Ipsen-Mikhailov method is a metric that compares adjacency matrices by quantifying their distance to each other [57]. Here, we interpreted adjacency matrix as a similarity matrix. For each exposure duration, similarity matrices were averaged hierarchically based on their closest distances for each data type, and then combined using an equal weighting method. Hence, for each exposure duration, consensus matrices were obtained.

This approach allowed us to identify robust consensus similarity matrices that consider both shared KE and associated BMDL values. Based on these consensus matrices, we identified five clusters at short-term and three clusters at intermediate-term exposure duration, indicating that KE-based MOA and ENM potency are relevant parameters to find commonalities between ENM exposures (Fig. 6). Next, we aimed to comprehend those biological events often shared within these groups. Exploring clusters determined in the short-term, we observed inflammatory events are often associated with Cluster 1 and 2, and those clusters are mainly composed of titanium and carbon-based ENM exposures to lung *in vivo* system. The complexity of the *in vivo* exposure systems, consisting of multiple types of cells and exhibiting high dynamism in bloodstream distribution, could have amplified the inflammatory response. In cluster 1 and 2, we noticed inflammatory related events, for example, secretion of proinflammatory mediators,

Fig. 5. ENM potency was associated with sensitivity of biological response in the AOP framework. A) Enrichment score ($-\log_{10}(\text{p-value})$) of p-values were computed across experiments using one-sided Fisher's test for statistical significance to identify dose categories enriched at specific biological scale of the response. B) Enrichment score ($-\log_{10}(\text{p-value})$) of p-values were computed across experiments using one-sided Fisher's test for statistical significance to identify dose categories enriched at specific stage of the response. KEs were considered collectively across all exposures at each exposure duration. Values above red dashed line mark features that have a p-value lower than 0.05, indicating significant enrichment.

recruitment of inflammatory cells, inflammatory events caused by phototoxicity, and suppression of inflammatory cytokines (Figure S4A and B). Interestingly, we observed that ENM exposures in THP-1 cell lines clustered with lung exposures *in vivo*. The plausibility of this finding is supported by a recent study that has suggested THP-1 has characteristics that potentially allow a mechanistic translatability towards lung *in vivo* system [5]. This aspect is considerably relevant given the current need for *in vitro-in vivo* extrapolation (IVIVE) and reduced animal testing.

In cluster 3, glucocorticoid receptor-related KEs are the most frequent, indicating that ENM from this group could be potential endocrine-disruptors, causing also inflammatory and immune response (Figure S4C) [58]. Previous studies have shown that disturbances in the activity of glucocorticoid receptors have been associated to inflammation, metabolic dysfunction, and immune disease. This can be explained

by the characteristics of cell lines from gastrointestinal system, which have high energy demands and function as cell barriers and are representative of this cluster [59]. In cluster 4, we observed KEs related to collagen accumulation and deposition alongside angiogenesis (Figure S4D), all of which have been closely associated with the development of fibrosis. Previous works have evidenced a correlation between fibroblast proliferation and collagen production to *in vivo* pro-fibrotic process [41]. Studies included in this group comprise mainly lung system exposed to distinct MWCNT. Moreover, fibrosis is a widely recognized endpoint of MWCNT-induced toxicity [60]. In cluster 5, cell death mechanisms, such as apoptosis, were the most frequently enriched KEs (Figure S4E), comprising copper and cristobalite silica-based ENM exposure in lung-based biological systems, which is in accordance with existing observations found in the literature for ENM that share similar chemical composition [61,62].

Fig. 6. Common biological patterns across ENM exposure studies per exposure duration. Consensus hierarchical clustering of ENM exposures based on the induced KE-based MOA and potency at A) short-term and B) intermediate-term. GSE accession number represents gene expression data series identifier from GEO database, for more details see Methods. Refer to [Table S1](#) for details on the individual GSE.

At the intermediate-term exposure duration, cluster 1 was mainly composed of iron-incorporated mesoporous silica-based ENM that possess distinct surface chemistry (e.g., lipidic, pegylated, and pristine). Nonetheless, these materials exhibit overall similar responses in liver-based cell lines. Among the KEs most frequently shared, there were KEs related to perturbation in lipid metabolism (represented by cholesterol and fatty acid metabolism alterations), xenobiotic response, and oxidative stress ([Figure S4F](#)). Such alterations have also been previously identified in other studies exposing *in vitro* liver cell and *in vivo* biological systems to chemically similar materials [63,64]. Cluster 2 was predominantly characterized by changes in cell proliferation, collagen metabolism and production of pulmonary serum amyloid A (SAA) ([Figure S4G](#)). Given there is a sensitized model for an asthma-like condition and that copper-based ENM have been shown to contribute to tissue remodeling [65,66], such KE could signify an ongoing repair process that could lead to resolution or aggravation of the condition inducing pulmonary fibrosis [67]. Cluster 3 was the largest cluster at this exposure period, including copper, carbon, and titanium-based ENM, and was marked by an unbalanced systemic inflammation and immune response ([Figure S4H](#)). Such biological responses are supported by recent findings in the literature [68–70].

Time-dependent direct MOA and potency-dependent KE progression apply to a specific cluster

Next, we aimed to understand if this grouping approach could recapitulate our main observations about (i) the time-dependent mechanisms induced by the exposure and (ii) influence of ENM potency in the progression of events, at a local context. To assess this, we selected one cluster of each exposure period as our case study. To increase the reliability, the selection was done based on the number of corresponding experiments. As a result, cluster 3 at short-term and cluster 1 at intermediate-term were chosen due to the largest number of ENM exposures that were common between clusters, about 3.

Interestingly, we noticed pronounced and comparable outcomes. KEs associated to genotoxic responses were found enriched at intermediate-term exposure duration. Additional specific functional effects were also evident (“lysosomal dysfunction” at short-term and “microtubule

dynamics altered” at intermediate-term) for the cluster at short-term and intermediate-term. However, these functional effects were not specific in the global analysis ([Figure S5](#)). Then, these KEs were systematically mapped in the AOP network and enriched AOPs to which they belong were highlighted ([Figure S6](#)). For instance, AOP:296 (*Oxidative DNA damage leading to chromosomal aberrations and mutations*) and AOP:46 (*Mutagenic Mode-of-Action leading to Hepatocellular Carcinoma*). Similarly, concerning the association of KE progression with ENM potency, we performed a Fisher-test enrichment and observed that high potency (i.e., lower triggering doses) associated KEs were overrepresented at basic KEs (p-value < 0.05) whereas lower potency (i.e., higher triggering doses) associated KEs were overrepresented at advanced KEs (p-value < 0.05) ([Figure S7A and B](#)). In addition, there was a significant difference between potencies at shorter and longer exposure duration (Student-*t*-test, p-value < 0.05). High potency was once more linked to shorter exposure time and low potency to longer exposure time ([Figure S7C and D](#)).

The emergence of the grouping might be influenced by the combined effects of chemical composition, biological system and size-related ENM features

Given the commonalities of molecular response induced by distinct ENM exposures, we hypothesized that similarity in the mechanisms is not solely centered on ENM chemical composition, but instead dependent on biological system exposed and extrinsic (e.g., colloidal stability and nano bio interface interactions) and intrinsic (e.g., size, surface charge and area, and chemistry) ENM properties. To specifically identify these driving factors, we used a gradient-boosted decision trees-based classification algorithm to predict the previously defined clusters ([Fig. 6](#)). We observed that ENM exposure characteristics, especially chemical composition, size-dependent properties of ENM, and biological system are the main predictors of the grouping ([Fig. 7](#)). To rank those features in order of relevance, we chose models generated using features with at least 60 % of data completeness achieving an optimal balance of performance ([Table S2](#)) and data coverage ([Table S3](#)). In general, the ranked features were consistent with our observations ([Fig. 7](#)).

Upon examining the ranked features, at both exposure duration (short- and intermediate-term), our findings indicate that biological

Fig. 7. Common and specific exposure characteristics influence grouping. Feature importance analysis for overall classification with varying percentage of data completeness to the prediction of ENM group based on a XGBoost algorithm. Percentage of data completeness represents the threshold chosen to ensure a minimum level of feature data coverage, increasing reliability in the model's prediction. Feature completeness indicates the data coverage associated with a particular feature. Average feature contribution represents how much the feature in the dataset influences the model's prediction. The higher these parameters are the more reliable and influential the feature is in the model's prediction.

system has an important impact in the grouping, which is represented by the contribution of biological descriptors (intrinsic features of biological system), such as exposure type and test system. Moreover, the chemical composition and extrinsic properties that represent ENM colloidal transformations (agglomeration and aggregation) were also deemed relevant (n and S parameters), of which are size-dependent properties [71]. Interestingly, in different exposure periods, we identified also specific features influencing the grouping. At short-term, dimension measured by dynamic light scattering techniques and system dependent features that consider the influence of nano bio interface interactions were evident [72]. Among them were ester group representing interactions of ENM-lipids (A.EST_Kb300k) and glycine representing ENM-aminoacids (A.GLY_Kb300k). At intermediate-term, properties related to size- and surface- characteristics properties were observed. Including size-related features examined by transmission electron

microscopy (TEM) and surface characteristics reflecting surface area and charge.

Hence, our results reinforce existing hypotheses that both original parameters that represent the ENM characteristics before and after contact with biological environment (i.e., mimicking real exposure context) are crucial to robustly represent ENM interactions with the biological environment [73,74]. Moreover, we showed that the choice of the test system may strongly affect the induced response as previously stated by other studies [23,52]. A recent analysis has shown that distinct biological response of ENM exposures in a harmonised dataset was clustering by biological system and emphasized the importance of accounting for this molecular build up effect when assessing ENM hazard potential [5]. While the influence of biological system features, ENM properties, and exposure duration on the ENM induced response is known, these conclusions often lack an integrated analysis. Indeed,

analyzing factors in isolation may overlook the complex interdependency and interactions among them. Unlike previous studies, we grouped ENM based on response similarities, considering sensitivity and type of response. This holistic approach allowed us to identify patterns that reflect the combined influence of these factors, acknowledging the complexity of biological response.

Network representation reveals crucial associations between the features

Next, we assessed whether the features, with minimum of 60 % of data completeness, were dependent between each other, contributing to the grouping. We hypothesized that each feature exerts influence on the others and that a network representation of features interaction highlights the most relevant features. Indeed, those features do not influence individually the models but instead act co-ordinately contributing to the grouping (Fig. 8A and B). Features related to the colloidal stability were not determining anymore for the grouping at intermediate-term. At short-term, results suggest larger connections between features, in number and strength of interactions and diversity of features, (Fig. 8A) compared to intermediate-term (Fig. 8B), which could be associated to the type of response. Nonetheless, it should be noted that the data is unbalanced across the exposure periods, especially when looking at the intermediate-term concerning the exposure system, but there is still a notable diversity when considering ENM characteristics. In particular, cluster 1 was driven mainly by the biological system features and diameter of ENM, while clusters 2 and 3 by intrinsic (diameter, surface area and charge) and extrinsic (n) ENM features, see Figure S8.

Our analysis supports the idea that early molecular responses are generally rapid and transient changes in gene expression, in a way that might be noisier due to variability in the molecular response dynamics in the initial contact, while longer ones might involve more sustained alterations overtime for which the system had time to adapt at higher systemic levels. A comparable notion has been reported recently emphasizing stronger intercellular communication immediately following exposure in which the response over time may evolve to resolution or progression to the potential AO [53].

Conclusions

Despite the incomplete knowledge about ENM hazard, ENM production continues to grow highlighting the need for efficient safety

assessment strategies to keep the pace. A dose-dependent analysis of toxicogenomics data allowed to characterize the underlying direct MOA and to determine the potency of ENM considered in this study. We successfully linked these direct molecular alterations to the AOP framework to identify an AOP-informed MOA. We observed that exposure duration influences the ENM elicited responses and that potency affects the progression of response. Based on these observations, we developed an integrated grouping approach based on dose-dependent analysis, potency evaluation and AOP-based modeling.

Despite the variations in response, our approach identified common molecular paths in response to groups of ENM and factors governing this grouping. Though, our approach highlights hazard difference between ENM exposure groups, we do not include a comparative analysis with the bulk counterparts of these materials. This focus on grouping of ENM hazards arises from their unique properties and known differences in toxicity compared to conventional counterparts. Integrating both aspects into a single analysis could reduce the accuracy of our predictions. While some studies have shown significant differences in ion release and biomolecular interactions [28,75], another study found that responses to various metal-based ENM were similar to those of their corresponding metal ions [51]. This applied to both essential and non-essential ENM, regardless of their known physiological function. Our approach could eventually be extended to bulk materials, but additional research is needed to effectively simultaneously integrate nano and its corresponding bulk materials.

Our findings indicate that considering the interplay of multifactorial exposure characteristics, beyond chemically-centered factors, is important for grouping distinct ENM exposures. Of those, size-dependent properties, chemical composition, and biological system features were highlighted. Although various studies highlight the impact of ENM properties, exposure duration, and biological system features in the ENM induced response, these findings often are considered in isolation. Our study addresses this by applying a grouping strategy that offers a mechanistic and multiscale understanding of response and elucidates important aspects of ENM exposure to be considered for an efficient ENM grouping. This approach is unique in its ability to synthesize data from numerous studies to identify meaningful groupings.

Our study complements the current approaches in ENM hazard assessment, supporting NAMs and SSbD methods and providing a valuable insight into ENM grouping. The impact of experimental variables on the observed response highlights the need for more diverse

Fig. 8. Features relevant for the grouping exhibit intricate relationships and reflect distinct response dynamics. Feature interactions were extracted and averaged based on 50 model's prediction ensuring a minimum of 60 % of data completeness. A) at short-term and B) intermediate-term. ENM features are represented by nodes and relationships between features are represented by undirected edges. Node size refers to the average feature contribution of the ENM feature and edge thickness, the strength of the interaction between ENM features.

ENM exposure datasets to increase its generalizability potential. While the collection of ENM exposures considered here is one of the largest with in-depth characterization (including experimental and predicted ENM features) and most heterogeneous in experimental setups considered, we do not address all existing ENM on the market. Moreover, at intermediate-term, we have a predominance of *in vivo* experiments as compared to *in vitro*, albeit the dose ranges were carefully corrected to reduce bias.

Despite these limitations, our strategy paves the way for the development of quantitative AOPs based on the modeling of KE relationships by considering dose-dependent transitions spanning levels of biological organization and, subsequently, IVIVE. Our study elucidates important aspects of ENM exposure to be considered for an efficient ENM grouping. Based upon BMD modeling and the AOP framework, our work establishes necessary connection to promote a mechanistic and multiscale perspective on the response elicited by exposure to ENM. This framework streamlines a more informative understanding of ENM hazard easing interpretation and generalization. If integrated with current guidelines, it can help to expedite current safety evaluation by leveraging a data-driven viewpoint. Importantly, this distinct initiative has not been explored by previous attempts.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Angela Serra: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Dario Greco:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Marcella Torres Maia:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Michele Fratello:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology. **Giusy del Giudice:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Laura Aliisa Saarimäki:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Lena Möbus:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT to improve clarity and readability of text. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.nantod.2025.102639](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nantod.2025.102639).

Data Availability

The intermediate data needed to replicate our findings are provided in the supplementary materials. Original can be obtained from (10.5281/zenodo.3949889; 10.5281/zenodo.7674574).

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